

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF INTERFACIAL REACTIONS DURING THE FABRICATION OF TITANIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Reactions in titanium matrix composites (TMCs) during fabrication have been investigated by considering thermodynamics and kinetics of the metallurgical systems at the composite interfaces. The tendency of the reaction product formation for both TiC and Ti₅Si₃ has been examined based on thermochemical data and phase diagrams available in the literature. It has been shown that, although, with the conventional heating technique, it is not feasible to prepare TMCs with the liquid infiltration technique due to extensive interfacial reactions, with a rapid infrared infiltration technique, TMCs reinforced with either carbon or silicon carbide fibers have been successfully manufactured. A relatively short processing time and the formation of a TiC diffusion barrier are the two factors facilitating the infrared infiltration technique. Results indicate that continuous TiC layers are formed on carbon or carbon coated SiC fiber surfaces at the beginning of the infiltration process. Thus, the fiber attack by the molten titanium alloy was minimal. Experimental observations agree well with the thermodynamic and kinetic analyses.

Keywords: titanium matrix composite, SiC fibers, carbon fibers, rapid infrared forming, interfacial reactions, fiber dissolution, thermodynamics, kinetics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to the light weight, high room temperature strength and modulus and strength retention at elevated temperatures, titanium matrix composites are strong candidates for structural application in the aerospace industries. Titanium matrix composites (TMCs) reinforced with SiC fibers are commonly fabricated by solid state diffusion bonding techniques such as the powder cloth technique or metal foil technique with hot pressing. However, these techniques can be successfully used only to incorporate relatively large size fibers in matrices. Moreover, long exposures to elevated temperatures, needs for pressurizing equipment and vacuum requirements make these composites expensive. Liquid infiltration is, relatively, a much lower cost process. However, because of the extent of the reaction between molten titanium and carbon or SiC fibers during fabrication, the liquid infiltration technique has not received much attention. The present authors are aware of only one attempt by Toloui [1] to fabricate a composite of a titanium-copper alloy reinforced with carbon fibers. In Toloui's approach, the composites produced had extensively degraded fibers due to long exposures of fibers in molten titanium alloys and hence very poor mechanical properties.

In order to ensure the success of the liquid infiltration process, ways to minimize the reaction at the interface must be developed. These methods may include shortening the processing time, coating the reinforcement fibers with a material that acts as a barrier to diffusing species, or incorporating alloying elements that retard the reaction. With the aim of minimizing the interfacial reaction during composite fabrication, a technique of making TMCs, applying a rapid infrared forming (RIF)

process, has been developed at the University of Cincinnati [2-6]. The RIF technique takes only 1 - 2 minutes in an inert environment at an atmospheric pressure for the composite fabrication. Due to very short processing times, reactions at the interface are limited and effectively controlled.

The reaction zones in rapid infrared formed C/Ti composites are in the order of 1 μ m which is substantially smaller than those of about 5 μ m in C/Ti-25wt%Cu composites produced by Toloui [1]. The strengths of the 40 vol% C/Ti alloy composites produced by the RIF technique were in the order of 1100 MPa which are significantly higher than values of 184 MPa for 30 vol% C/Ti-25wt%Cu composites produced by Toloui [1]. Comparing with the diffusion bonded SiC/Ti alloy composites, the rapid infrared formed SCS-6/Ti alloy composites exhibit a smaller reaction zone and superior mechanical properties. While essentially no reaction was observed in RIF composites, it appears as though the outer pyrocarbon layers were partially dissolved. The reaction zone thicknesses were about 2.0 μ m in Ti-24Al-11Nb/SCS-6 composites produced by the powder cloth diffusion bonding technique [7] and about 5 μ m in Ti-48Al-1Ta/SCS-6 composites produced by hot pressing [8]. The strength and modulus of 23 vol% SCS-6/Ti alloy RIF composites [6] prepared in this laboratory are, respectively, 1734 MPa and 195 GPa, which are again superior to 1180 MPa and 200 GPa for 30-40 vol% SCS-6/Ti-24Al-11Nb composites [7] and 1455 MPa and 225 GPa for Ti-6Al-4V/SCS-6 composites [9] reported in the literature. Table 1 summarizes the mechanical properties of some of the alloys, reinforcements and composites available in the literature along with the RIF composites and alloys. In this paper, we will explore the thermodynamic and kinetic fundamentals of interfacial reactions during the liquid infiltration of titanium matrix composites and verify these considerations with experiments on carbon and silicon carbide fiber reinforced titanium matrix composites prepared by the newly developed rapid infrared forming process.

Table 1. Tensile properties of some of the alloys, reinforcements and titanium matrix composites

Material	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Reference
C fiber (P-55)	1730	379	10
SCS-6 fiber	3950	400	11
Ti80 (as cast)	1290	118	6 *
Ti85 (as cast)	1600	120	2 *
Ti80/SCS-6 (23 vol%)	1734	195	6 *
Ti85/C (40 vol%)	1100	200	2 *
Ti-6Al-4V	890	110	9
Ti-6-4/SiC (35 vol%)	1455	225	9
Ti-6-4/SiC (35 vol%)	1690	186	12
Ti-15-3/SCS-6 (38-41 vol%)	1951	213	12
Ti-24Al-11Nb/SCS6 (30-40 vol%)	1180	200	7
Beta 21-S/SCS-6 (0-90)	1680	81	13 *

* Flexural test results from our laboratory

2. THERMODYNAMICS AND KINETICS OF INTERFACIAL REACTIONS

2.1. The Carbon Fiber/Ti Composite System

Reactions in titanium matrix composites during infiltration may be investigated by considering thermodynamics and kinetics of the metallurgical system at the interface. During infiltration, when liquid titanium comes in contact with carbon fibers, two competing processes could have happened. One is the formation of TiC on the carbon surface and the other is the dissolution of carbon in the molten titanium alloy. If the TiC formation rate is faster than the dissolution rate of carbon in molten titanium, a continuous TiC layer will form at the fiber surface. Once the initial TiC layer has formed, further growth of the TiC layer relies on the diffusion of carbon atoms outward or titanium atoms inward through the previously formed TiC layer. In the meantime, since no carbon exists in the original titanium alloy, the outer layer of TiC will gradually dissolve in the titanium alloy. Thus, both TiC growth and dissolution is expected until the carbon concentration in the alloy equals that in

equilibrium with liquid Ti and TiC, after which the TiC dissolution stops while diffusion controlled TiC growth continues. At the TiC-alloy interface, the concentration of carbon should be the saturated carbon content as indicated in the Ti-C phase diagram [14]. Assuming that carbon, being only in a small amount in the liquid titanium alloy, follows the Henrian behavior and that Ti, being greater than 70 mole percent in the liquid alloy, follows the Raoultian behavior, the activity of carbon, a_C , in equilibrium with the liquid titanium alloy and TiC can be calculated. From free energy data available in the literature [15,16] for the following reaction,

where (l) stands for liquid, (gr) for graphite and (s) for solid, the activity of carbon in equilibrium with solid TiC and liquid Ti alloy with a titanium activity of 0.9 at 1300 °C was calculated as equal to 2.82×10^{-6} . From the activity and composition data, obtained from the free energy calculations and the phase diagram, respectively, the Henrian constant ($\gamma_{H,C}$) was calculated at various temperatures. The partial molar enthalpy of mixing of carbon in liquid titanium was determined and the value of $\gamma_{H,C}$ at 1300 °C was extrapolated to be 5.63×10^{-4} . The carbon concentration in mole fraction, X_C , in equilibrium with the liquid Ti alloy and TiC was estimated to be equal to 0.005. Such a low value of X_C suggests that only a small amount of carbon in the liquid titanium alloy is required for the formation of TiC. The low value of the Henrian constant suggests that the carbon atoms are tightly bonded to titanium atoms in the liquid alloy and hence causes a large negative deviation from ideality.

Away from the TiC surface, the carbon concentration will gradually reduce depending on the diffusion rate of carbon atoms in liquid Ti. Data from Toloui [1] indicated that the thickness of the TiC layer varies linearly with the square root of time. This observation suggests that the growth of TiC is a diffusion controlled process at the temperature range of this study. It also indicates that the rate of TiC dissolution in molten Ti is slow compared to the TiC growth, and thus, the reduction in TiC thickness due to dissolution does not affect the parabolic relationship between the TiC thickness and time. However, their study was done for relatively long times, and hence there was sufficient time for the saturation of the alloy with carbon. Thus, the initial competing mechanisms may not have been observable.

On the other hand, should the dissolution of carbon prevail instead of TiC formation, a continuous layer of TiC does not form at the fiber surface. Initially, the fibers would dissolve in the alloy till the concentration of carbon required for the formation of TiC is reached. The formation of TiC will start with the nucleation of TiC particles in supersaturated titanium liquid. Experiments from this laboratory did not show evidence of such phenomena.

2.2. The SiC Fiber/Ti Composite System

In the SiC/Ti system, calculations based on the reaction,

indicate that when the liquid titanium alloy comes in contact with SiC, SiC becomes unstable and dissociates into Si and C, which are dissolved in the molten metal. For the reaction,

the activity of silicon, a_{Si} , in equilibrium with $\text{Ti}_5\text{Si}_3\text{(s)}$ and the liquid titanium alloy with a Ti activity of 0.9 at 1300 °C was calculated as 2.28×10^{-7} . The Henrian constant of Si in liquid Ti, $\gamma_{H,Si}$, at 1300 °C was 2.117×10^{-6} . The mole fraction of Si, X_{Si} , in equilibrium with the liquid Ti alloy and Ti_5Si_3 at 1300 °C was estimated from the binary phase diagram of the Ti-Si system to be equal to 0.11. This relatively high value of X_{Si} suggests that the concentration of silicon in the liquid alloy required for Ti_5Si_3 formation is large and hence a large amount of fiber dissolution must occur before the formation of Ti_5Si_3 . For a 30 vol% SiC fiber reinforced composite with a fiber diameter of 142 μm , it can be shown that the SiC fiber would dissolve to a depth of about 0.3 μm before TiC

can form and to a depth of about 35 μm before Ti_5Si_3 can form. This calculation assumes that Si and C spread through out the titanium matrix instantly after the SiC dissolution. In other words, the tendency of forming TiC in the molten titanium alloy is about two orders of magnitude higher than that of Ti_5Si_3 formation as SiC dissolves. In the SiC/Ti system, earlier studies [4] have shown that the TiC formation is not continuous. Unlike the C/Ti system, there is no continuous TiC layer on the SiC fiber surface to act as a barrier for further interfacial reaction. Thus, dissolution continues to occur until a large amount of fiber is consumed.

The Ti-Si-C ternary phase diagram at 1300 °C with super cooled Ti liquid (Figure 1) can be estimated from a study of the system in the literature [17]. As SiC dissolves in the liquid titanium, concentrations of C and Si, roughly equal due to stoichiometric dissolution of SiC, follow the dotted line in Figure 1. As the SiC dissolves in Ti(l), the solution will enter the two phase Ti(l) + TiC region and TiC will precipitate. Further dissolution will bring the systems into the ternary Ti + TiC + Ti_5Si_3 region, where both TiC and Ti_5Si_3 can precipitate. The phase diagram also shows a ternary phase T, corresponding to Ti_2SiC . From the phase diagram, this phase will not form until a significant amount of SiC has been dissolved in Ti(l).

Figure 1. The Ti-Si-C ternary phase diagram for the super cooled Ti liquid at 1300 °C

Finally, in the case of SCS-6/Ti composite system, since the carbon rich coating on the surface of the SiC fiber contains several layers of Si+C and C, thermodynamic and kinetic considerations would predict a complex reaction. SCS- 6 fibers have a 3 μm carbon-rich coating which consists of two separate layers of amorphous carbon separated by a region rich in silicon. In the coating, the silicon content exhibits a maximum value at the outer surface and at a distance of 1.5 μm from the surface [12]. When the alloy comes in contact with the Si+C layers, reactions similar to that of uncoated SiC fibers are expected and when the alloy comes in contact with the carbon layers, reactions would be similar to that in the carbon/Ti system. In fact, in the experiments conducted in our laboratory, the interfacial reaction between SCS-6 fibers and Ti alloys, is indeed, significantly lower than that between SCS-0 fibers and titanium alloys. The pyrolytic carbon coating on the silicon carbide fiber surface effectively retarded the dissolution of the SCS fibers.

3. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATIONS

3.1. Experimental Techniques

Titanium matrix composites used in this study were produced by the rapid infrared forming (RIF) technique. The process consisted of heating the fibers, either continuous P-55 carbon fibers from Union Carbide, SiC fibers (SCS-0, SCS-2 and SCS-6) from Textron Specialty Materials or Nicalon SiC fibers from Dow Corning, along with titanium-nickel alloys with a ternary addition (designated as Ti85, containing 85wt% Ti or Ti80, containing 80wt% Ti) at a rate of 200 °C/s in an inert atmosphere. Due to differences in the infrared absorption characteristics of different materials, selective heating of the crucible and the composite lay-up can be achieved without heating the furnace walls, facilitating high heating and cooling rates. Measured amounts of the fiber (35 vol%, continuous P-55 carbon fibers or SiC fibers) and the alloy were placed in a graphite crucible. Infiltration was done at 1350 °C for 10 seconds to fabricate C/Ti85 composites, at 1250 °C for 10 seconds to fabricate C/Ti80 composites and at 1200 °C for 30 seconds to fabricate SiC/Ti80 composites.

In order to study the interfacial reaction characteristics of as processed samples, all samples were cut perpendicular to the fiber axis with a slow speed diamond saw. They were mounted and polished with SiC papers to remove the epoxy and make the surface flat. Further polishing was done with diamond pastes to a 1 μ m finish. The samples were sputtered with gold and viewed under a Cambridge 600 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with an energy dispersive x-ray (EDX) analysis and elemental mapping facility.

3.2. Experimental Results and Discussion

SEM secondary electron images of interfaces in C/Ti80 and C/Ti85 composites processed at 1250 °C and 1350 °C for 10 seconds, respectively, indicate that during processing, a thin continuous layer of TiC, on the order of 1 μ m, forms at the fiber surface as demonstrated by micrographs of C/Ti80 composite cross section in Figure 2. Toloui [1], during liquid infiltration of C/Ti-25wt%Cu and C/Ti-35wt%Cu composites using induction heating, observed that the increase in the reaction zone thickness was controlled by the diffusion of elements across the TiC layer. Although those observations were made for relatively long time exposures, typically in the order of 240 seconds to 720 seconds, deductions from previous work by the authors with the C/Ti alloy system [2,3] suggest that even for very short processing times, typically in the order of 10-30 seconds, when Ti comes in contact with carbon fibers, a thin continuous layer of TiC forms at the interface preventing further dissolution of the fibers.

Figure 2. Secondary electron image of the interface in a C/Ti80 composites fabricated by the rapid infrared forming technique, showing a thin continuous layer of TiC at the interface.

In the SiC/Ti system, earlier studies [4] have shown that unlike the C/Ti system, there is no continuous TiC layer formed on the SiC fiber surface to act as a barrier for further interfacial reaction. Thus, dissolution continues to occur until a large amount of fiber is consumed, as seen in Figure 3. Similar results were also observed with Nicalon SiC fibers infiltrated with Ti80 alloy at 1280°C for 30 seconds. As seen from Figure 4, almost all the fibers were completely dissolved in the alloy. Since the size of the Nicalon SiC fibers are in the order of 10-15 μm, which is very small compared to SiC fibers (SCS-0) from Textron Specialty Material, almost all the fibers have been completely reacted. Although free carbon exists in Nicalon fibers, it appears to have no effect on the dissolution of SiC as no continuous TiC layer forms and hence dissolution is not retarded.

Figure 3. Secondary electron micrographs of the fiber-matrix interaction zone in SCS-0/Ti80 composites fabricated at 1200 °C for 30 seconds.

Figure 4. Optical micrograph of the cross section of Nicalon SiC/Ti80 composites fabricated at 1280 °C for 30 seconds, showing almost completely dissolved fibers.

In the case of SiC fibers with pyrocarbon coatings, as in the SCS-6/Ti system shown in Figure 5(a), the dissolution of the SiC fibers does not occur. SCS-6 fibers have a 3 μm carbon-rich coating which consists of two layers of amorphous carbon separated by a region rich in silicon. In the coating, the silicon content exhibits a maximum value at the outer surface and at a distance of 1.5 μm

Figure 5. Fiber-matrix interface in SCS-6/Ti80 composites fabricated at (a) 1250 °C for 10 seconds and (b) 1250 °C for 60 seconds

from the surface [12]. As seen from Figure 5(a), the interface consists of two layers. The outer layer is believed to be the carbon layer below the second silicon rich region. The layer next to the fibers is the Si+C layer in between the fiber and the carbon layer. It appears that the original outer most carbon rich layer on the fibers were consumed during the fabrication process. The top layer of the coating comprises Si+C. This layer does not act as a barrier to dissolution since a continuous TiC layer cannot form. The outer most carbon layer, about 0.5 μm , in thickness is believed to have reacted in a way similar to the C/Ti system. As in the C/Ti system, competing mechanisms would dictate the extent of the interaction. With short processing times, 10 seconds at 1250° C, the competing mechanism permits the dissolution of only the outer three layers (one carbon and two Si+C), whereas with longer processing times, 60 seconds at 1250°C, all the coatings were dissolved and the fibers were severely attacked, Figure 5(b), similar to the condition in uncoated SiC/Ti composites.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From thermodynamic and kinetic considerations, the interfacial reactions during liquid infiltration of titanium matrix composites have been investigated. As a result of the rapid interaction between molten titanium alloys and SiC or C fibers, the liquid infiltration technique for making titanium matrix composites is only feasible with very fast processes like the rapid infrared forming technique developed at the University of Cincinnati. Titanium matrix composites fabricated with this technique have limited and well controlled interfacial reactions. It is believed that carbon fibers and carbon coated SiC fibers form continuous TiC layers which prevent further dissolution of the fibers. On the other hand, uncoated SiC fibers, such as SCS-0 and Nicalon fibers, were extensively dissolved in the liquid titanium alloy even during rapid infrared infiltration. This study suggests that using SCS-6 fibers with thicker carbon coatings or SiC fibers with only carbon coatings as reinforcements would improve the dissolution resistance of SiC fibers during liquid infiltration. Thermodynamic analysis of the C/Ti and SiC/Ti systems agrees well with the observed interfacial reaction in these composites.

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METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES: PROCESSING
